

INFORMATION ASYMMETRY IN THE BANKING SECTOR: A ZIMBABWEAN SCENARIO

Thabani Nyoni

Department of Economics,
University of Zimbabwe, Harare-Zimbabwe

ABSTRACT

The banking sector in Zimbabwe recently witnessed closure of several banks. It is important to note that although there are many reasons for such bank closures; information asymmetry is also one of the issues that led to bank failure and the consequent closure of banks in Zimbabwe. This paper looks at how information asymmetry could be subscribed to bank closure in Zimbabwe. The paper, amongst other possible solutions to information asymmetry; encourages players in the banking sector to reduce information asymmetry by properly gathering and analyzing information about borrowers.

Key Words: Adverse selection, Banking sector, Bounded rationality, Credit rationing, Information asymmetry, Interest rate, Moral hazard, Zimbabwe

1. INTRODUCTION:

The fundamental reason why people give their money to financial intermediaries instead of lending or investing the money directly is because of the risk that is present from the information asymmetry between the provider of funds and the receiver of those funds. A seller knows more about sale item than the buyer. So the buyer would be taking a risk buying the item. The buyer asks, why is the seller selling? Likewise, a borrower knows more about his financial condition and his future prospects than the lender [4]. Information asymmetry can be operationally defined as those situations, in which some agent(s) in a trade possesses information while other agent(s) involved in the same trade do not. Information asymmetry basically results in adverse selection, moral hazard and monitoring costs.

One of the basic functions of banks is to gather information about borrowers and screen creditworthy borrowers from non-credit worthy ones. The bulk of this information is obtained in the process of lending and in the subsequent monitoring role that is often seen as defining characteristic of bank financing. However, information asymmetry in credit markets constitutes the backbone of the financial ineffectiveness, financial crisis and the ultimate bank closures [4].

The asymmetric information literature which looks at the impact of financial structure on economic activity focuses on the differences in information available to different parties in a

financial contract. Borrowers have an informational advantage over lenders because borrowers know more about the investment projects they want to undertake [6]. This informational advantage results in adverse selection and the classic “lemons” problem first described by [1].

2. CHARACTERISING THE LEMONS PROBLEM

For the sake of expagoration, suppose there are two economic agents, a seller and a buyer of a used car; each has to make a decision. The seller who is selling the car knows, whether the car is a good car or a bad car (a lemon); on the other hand the buyer is not aware of anything concerning the quality of the used car but just has an idea about the probability distribution of good cars and bad cars. In this regard, symmetric information prevents the market from achieving Pareto efficiency.

The lemons problem described in this case also represents adverse selection, a situation in which less desirable economic agents are likely to commercially engage as the information is insufficient in order to determine the true quality of the exchanged commodity. Within the context of the Lemons phenomenon, adverse selection is shown by considering the buyers who cannot determine the level of quality of the desired used car. Therefore, there are used cars with various qualities and differing real monetary values, and yet within a particular price range.

Imagine the minimum price of a used car is \$800 USD - \$3500 USD, but they are going to be sold at an identical price of \$3000 USD. What it implies is that some buyers will be acquiring a lemon with its true value of \$800 USD, while the owners of high-quality cars will have no buyers at all because they will be asking for higher prices.

A lemons problem occurs in the debt market because lenders have trouble determining whether a borrower is a good risk (he has good investment opportunities with low risk) or, alternatively, is a bad risk (he has poorer investment projects with high risk). If the lender cannot distinguish between the borrowers of good quality and bad quality (the lemons), he will only make the loan at an interest rate that reflects the average quality of the good and bad borrowers. The result is that high-quality borrowers will be paying a higher interest rate than they should because low-quality borrowers pay a lower interest rate than they should. One result of this lemons problem is that some high-quality borrowers may drop out of the market, with what would have been profitable investment projects not being undertaken [6].

3. CAN ZIMBABWE’S RECENT BANK CLOSURES BE SUBSCRIBED TO INFORMATION ASYMMETRY?

In this regard the recent closure of banks in Zimbabwe can be attributed to information asymmetry in the context of the “lemons” problem. Banks in Zimbabwe continue to have a lot of trouble in determining a good borrower, probably due to bounded rationality which means that banks cannot solve information asymmetry perfectly, costlessly and instantaneously. Because of that, banks in Zimbabwe resort to charging interest rates that reflect the average quality of the good and bad borrowers.

This therefore implies that good borrowers (low risk borrowers) pay high interest rates than they should pay, while bad borrowers (high risk borrowers) pay less interest rates than they should. This drives away good borrowers and the banking sector is left with “lemons”. This is what has happened recently in Zimbabwe. Interest rates charged by local banks have been so high that most investors have found it better to opt out of the financial markets by withdrawing their deposits from their respective banks resulting in the recent closure of such banks as Genesis Investment Bank, Interfin Bank, Royal Bank and Zimbabwe Allied Banking Group (ZABG) among others.

Another result, as demonstrated by [12], is that information asymmetry can result in credit rationing in which some borrowers are arbitrarily denied loans. This occurs because a higher interest rate leads to even greater adverse selection: the borrowers with the riskiest investment projects will now be the likeliest to want to take out loans at the higher interest rate. If the lender cannot identify the borrowers with the riskier investment projects, he may want to cut down the number of loans he makes, which causes the supply of loans to decrease rather than increase with the higher interest rate.

Thus, even if there is an excess demand for loans, a higher interest rate will not equilibrate the market because additional increases in the interest rate will only decrease the supply of loans and worsen the excess demand for loans even further. Therefore, a small rise in the riskless interest rate has the potential to lead to a very large decrease in lending and possibly even a collapse in the market.

In Zimbabwe credit rationing, coupled with information asymmetry has resulted in banks lending to borrowers of high risk profile unknowingly. According to [11], the bank might have to rely on a few observable characteristics of a borrower, even though signs do not address all the risk of the particular loan. Credit rationing based on characteristics of the borrower has resulted in the recent closure of some banks in Zimbabwe because such signs are not enough to address all the risk profile of the particular borrower.

The adverse selection-lemons analysis above indicates how a disruption can occur in financial markets that adversely affects aggregate economic activity. If market interest rates are driven up sufficiently because of increased demand for credit or because of a decline in the money supply, the adverse selection problem might dramatically worsen and there will be a significant decline in lending, which, in turn, results in a substantial decrease in investment and aggregate economic activity. In addition, if uncertainty increases in a financial market such that it becomes harder for lenders to screen out good borrowers from bad borrowers, the adverse selection problem would also increase dramatically and, again, could lead to a sharp decline in investment and aggregate activity [6].

These mechanisms generally suggest that an important manifestation of a financial crisis would be a large rise in interest rates to borrowers for whom there is substantial difficulty in obtaining reliable information about their characteristics; that is, for whom there is a serious asymmetric information problem. At the same time, there would be a much smaller effect on interest rates to borrowers for whom almost no asymmetric information problem exists because information about their characteristics is easily obtainable.

Since low-quality borrowers are more likely to be those firms for which information about their characteristics is difficult to obtain, while high-quality borrowers are more likely to be ones for which the asymmetric information problem is least severe, a rise in the spread between interest rates on low-quality versus high quality bonds can provide information on when the adverse selection problem becomes more severe in debt markets [6].

Asymmetric information between borrowers and lenders also results in a moral hazard problem which affects the efficiency of financial markets. Because lenders have trouble ascertaining the quality of investment projects that borrowers wish to undertake, the borrower has incentives to engage in activities that may be personally beneficial but will increase the probability of default and thus harm the lender. For example, the borrower has incentives to cheat by misallocating funds for his own personal use, either through embezzlement or by spending on perquisites which do not lead to increased profits [6].

Also the borrower has incentives to undertake investment in unprofitable projects that increase his power or stature or to invest in projects with higher risk, in which the borrower does well if the project succeeds but the lender bears most of the loss if the project fails. In addition, the borrower has incentives to shirk and to just not work very hard. The conflict of interest between the borrower and lender (the agency problem) implies that lending and investment will be at suboptimal levels [6]. Indeed, as indicated by [2], a lower amount of a borrower's net-worth increases the agency problem because the borrower has less to lose by engaging in moral hazard.

The problem of moral hazard briefly discussed above, being an off-shoot trouble of information asymmetry; was often engaged into recently in Zimbabwe. For example, in the recent years there are farmers who borrowed money from certain banks in the name of Tobacco and Maize production. However, some of the so-called farmers actually bought themselves luxury cars and food staffs with the borrowed money. They chose to misuse the money and unfortunately, they allegedly went unpunished! This kind of moral hazard could also be attributed to the recent closure of banks in Zimbabwe since most borrowers just took the money and deliberately defaulted. The banks that had lent their money to those farmers experienced heavy losses and it can be argued that; that's why some of the banks had to close down.

Bank panics are clearly one major way for banks to find themselves unable to fully perform their intermediation role. In a panic, depositors, fearing the safety of their deposits,

withdraw them from the banking system, causing a contraction in loans and a multiple contraction in deposits [6]. Recently in Zimbabwe, most depositors have attempted to empty their bank accounts as the government introduced the Bond Notes. Depositors feared that their hard earned money could be lost as what happened during the 2008 hyperinflationary era when depositors' accounts were "frozen".

Here, again, an asymmetric information problem is at the source of the financial crisis because depositors rush to make withdrawals from solvent as well as insolvent banks since they cannot distinguish between them. Furthermore, banks' desire to protect themselves from possible deposit outflows leads them to increase their reserves relative to deposits, which also produces a contraction in loans and deposits. The net result is that a bank panic reduces the funds available to banks to make loans, and thus the cost of financial intermediation rises, causing a reduction in investment and a decline in aggregate economic activity.

A bank panic also has the feature of decreasing liquidity, which will lead to higher interest rates. Currently, there is low liquidity in the economy as already noted by [5] and [7-10] who clearly highlight the fact that there is literally no cash (in circulation) in the economy of Zimbabwe. Such a scenario encourages depositors to attempt to hoard hard cash (by requesting more withdrawals from their respective banks). This effectively reduces loanable funds within the banking system and in the long run causes bank failure. As we have seen before, the rise in interest rates directly increases adverse selection problems in credit markets and can reduce the value of firms' net worth, which also increases adverse selection as well as agency problems. Thus, since bank panics have the secondary effect of increasing adverse selection and agency problems in financial markets, they lead to economic contraction through these channels as well. We should then expect to see that bank panics are also associated with a larger interest-rate spread between higher- and lower-quality debt instruments.

4. SUGGESTED SOLUTIONS TO INFORMATION ASYMMETRY:

However, the above discussed problems of information asymmetry can be solved by the banks themselves. Before we discuss the solutions, it is important to bear in mind that these solutions will rarely be adequate because of bounded rationality associated with internalising the problems of information asymmetry that led to the closure of some banks in the Zimbabwe banking sector.

One way that lender can reduce the adverse selection problem in debt markets is to have the borrower provide collateral for the loan. Thus, if the borrower defaults on the loan, the lender can take title to the collateral and sell it to make up the loss. The problem in Zimbabwe has been associated with fact that some borrowers are politicians and because of that, in the event that they default the bank does not take title to collateral.

However, it is essential to note that if the collateral is of good enough quality, then it is no longer as important whether the borrower is of good or bad quality since the loss incurred by

the lender if the loan is defaulted on is substantially reduced. With collateral, therefore, the fact that there is asymmetric information between the borrower and lender is no longer as important a factor in the market.

Banks are eminently well suited to solve many of the adverse selection and moral hazard problems inherent in credit markets since they have expertise in collecting information about firms, and thus are better able to screen good borrowers from bad borrowers at a low cost. In this regard Zimbabwean banks can analyze the information that they gather about firms and individual borrowers and this will help them identify good borrowers. This is especially true, as put forward by [6]; that banks are not as subject to the free-rider problem which exists for individual purchasers of marketable securities who can costlessly take advantage of information that other purchasers of marketable securities produce.

The advantages of banks in information-collection activities are also enhanced by their ability to engage in long-term customer relationships and to issue loans using lines-of-credit arrangements [6].

In addition, they can engage in lower-cost monitoring than individuals, as is demonstrated in [3], and have advantages in enforcement of restrictive covenants, both of which reduce the potential for moral hazard by borrowers. In this way Zimbabwean banks reduce the consequences of information asymmetry in the financial markets and therefore avoid bank closures.

5. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS:

In conclusion, information asymmetry is NOT the only reason that can be attributed to the recent bank closures in Zimbabwe. There are also various other factors that led to the recent closure of banks in Zimbabwe and these include corporate governance issues, economic as well as political factors among other things. Players in the banking sector are encouraged to take note of the suggested possible solutions to information asymmetry in order to minimize bank failure.

REFERENCES:

- [1] Akerlof G (1970): The Market for Lemons: Quality Uncertainty and the Market Mechanism; *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 6 (2): 129 – 141
- [2] Bernanke B.S and Gertler M (1989): Agency Costs, Collateral and Business Fluctuations; *American Economic Review*, 21 (7): 633 – 662
- [3] Diamond D (1984): Financial Intermediation and Delegated Monitoring; *Review of Economic Studies*, 1 (1): 67 – 83
- [4] Kemei J C & Kerongo F (2014). The effects of information asymmetry in the performance of the banking industry: a case study of banks in Mombasa County, *International Journal of Education and Research*, 2(2): 1 – 6
- [5] Mhlanga F (2016). Cash crises threatens SMEs, *Zimbabwe Independent*, 4th of

November 2016

- [6] Mishkin F.S (1990): Financial Markets and Financial crises; *University of Chicago Press*; Chicago.
- [7] Mpofu B (2016). Chiwenga takes bond notes to the barracks, *Zimbabwe Independent*, 4th of November 2016
- [8] Nyoni T & Bonga W G (2017a). Towards Factors Affecting Delays in Construction Projects: A Case of Zimbabwe, *Dynamic Research Journals Journal of Economics and Finance (DRJ-JEF)*, 2(1):12 – 28
- [9] Nyoni T & Bonga W G (2017d). Cashless Transacting Economy: A Necessary Evil for Development! A Zimbabwean Scenario! *Dynamic Research Journals Journal of Economics and Finance (DRJ-JEF)*, 2(4):1 – 10
- [10] Nyoni T & Bonga W G (2017f). An Empirical Analysis of the Determinants of Private Investment in Zimbabwe, *Dynamic Research Journals Journal of Economics and Finance (DRJ-JEF)*, 2(4):38 – 54
- [11] Sachs J & Larraine F (1993). Macroeconomics in the global economy, *McGraw-Hill Publishers*, New York
- [12] Stiglitz J & Weiss A (1981): Credit Rationing in Markets with Imperfect Information; *American Economic Review*, 46 (19): 453 – 467